

Solar-Powered Rapid Charging System for Electric Vehicle Batteries Utilizing Fast Tag Technology

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Abstract— The document provides an in-depth analysis of a planning unit designed for an electric vehicle charging station circuit, with a specific focus on integrating RFID and manual entry inputs. It underscores the utilization of renewable energy sources, particularly solar power, for vehicle charging, with an emphasis on reducing reliance on the traditional grid and promoting environmentally friendly practices. The circuit incorporates various components such as RFID reader modules, LCD displays, matrix keyboards, regulated power supplies, and the Arduino Uno for programming functionality. Additionally, it delves into specific aspects like overvoltage protection during charging, the role of the Arduino Uno development board, the features of the LCD screen, and the inclusion of fire/flame sensor modules. The abstract encapsulates the convergence of technology, renewable energy utilization, and efficient charging methodologies within the electric vehicle infrastructure.

Keywords— Electric vehicles (EVs), Energy storage, solar panel, Li-ion batteries, RFID, IOT, Arduino-UNO R3

I. INTRODUCTION

The current slow charging of electric vehicles using AC charging hardware is inefficient and time-consuming, leading to a long charging time of up to 8 hours for EVs. However, the utilization of DC chargers promises faster and more efficient charging, addressing the need for a viable and cost-effective EV charging strategy while considering grid stability and charging demands from EV users. A new stochastic top-of-line charging system is being developed to efficiently charge EVs using renewable energy sources, ensuring grid stability and satisfying charging demands while minimizing overall charging costs. This initiative aims to contribute to reducing global warming by promoting sustainable transportation through the increased adoption of electric vehicles.

The rise in electric vehicle adoption is driven by the global push towards reducing emissions and addressing climate change. High petrol and diesel prices are also prompting people worldwide to shift towards electric vehicles, underscoring the need for efficient and fast EV charging solutions. In response to this trend, a team of engineers and researchers is pioneering the development of the FastTag Battery Charger to meet the increasing demand for convenient and rapid EV charging infrastructure.

The FastTag Battery Charger is a groundbreaking advancement in electric vehicle charging technology, designed to significantly decrease charging times while upholding safety and dependability. This innovative project goes beyond just quicker EV charging, aiming to seamlessly integrate charging into daily routines, alleviate range anxiety, and drive global EV adoption rates higher. Built on state-of-the-art power electronics, battery management, and communication technologies, the FastTag Battery Charger offers unprecedented charging speeds without sacrificing efficiency or battery longevity. It builds upon the success of current fast-charging solutions, overcoming their limitations to set new benchmarks in the EV charging landscape.

The development of the FastTag Battery Charger includes creating a modular charging infrastructure adaptable for both existing and new locations, catering to the increasing demand for fast-charging stations. Flexibility is key, ensuring the charging setup can evolve alongside the needs of individual EV owners and

fleet operators. Interoperability and compatibility with various EV models are prioritized, fostering a unified charging network that streamlines the EV charging experience globally.

Safety measures are at the core of the FastTag Battery Charger's design, featuring advanced thermal management, overcurrent protection, and secure communication protocols to enhance user confidence and reduce risks. The project also emphasizes sustainability, aiming to minimize energy waste and carbon emissions associated with EV charging, thereby promoting environmental stewardship in the transportation sector.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Electric vehicles are poised to become the dominant mode of transportation in the automotive industry due to their efficiency, low maintenance requirements, and minimal environmental impact. However, the transition to electric vehicles presents challenges, including limited range, long charging times, high initial costs, and the impact of non-linear loads on the power grid. The shifting from internal combustion-powered vehicles to electric vehicles poses challenges related to performance, grid impact, and achieving net zero pollution.

The drawbacks of current-generation electric vehicles include limited range, extended charging periods, high upfront costs, battery replacement needs, and subpar performance. Additionally, the introduction of non-linear loads to the grid can affect power quality, while the increased demand for energy due to EV utilization exacerbates the existing strain on power generation capacity.

The pollution stemming from internal combustion engines contributes significantly to global warming, prompting the need for alternative energy sources and methods to reduce emissions. Solar-based chargers offer a potential solution to these challenges and can improve EV performance through the adoption of new technologies. Centralizing charging stations, shifting towards renewable energy production, and leveraging solar and wind energy on a larger scale can work towards achieving a net zero carbon footprint and reducing dependency on fossil fuels. Furthermore, the adoption of solar-based fast-tag battery chargers for EVs presents an opportunity to decrease charging times and further reduce environmental impact.

The current EV chargers have different power ratings and output voltages, leading to varying charging times ranging from 17 hours for 3 kW chargers to approximately 1 hour for high-power DC chargers. Existing chargers rely on rectifier circuits to convert AC to DC, resulting in switching losses and decreased efficiency. However, our project primarily utilizes DC power directly from PV panels, eliminating the need for rectifier circuits and improving overall efficiency and cost-effectiveness.

To overcome the fluctuating DC voltage from PV panels, we have integrated a DC-DC Buck-Boost converter into our system design. This converter ensures a steady and consistent voltage output to effectively charge the EV battery, adjusting for input voltage fluctuations by acting as both a Buck and Boost converter as needed. Additionally, the inclusion of an Arduino UNO ATmega328 microcontroller, connected to an RFID system, streamlines operations by automatically monitoring and displaying voltage, current, and battery charge percentage on an LCD screen.

Our project aims to enhance EV charging efficiency by utilizing direct DC power from PV panels, reducing the reliance on rectifier circuits and incorporating intelligent control systems to optimize charging performance. The integration of a DC-DC Buck-Boost converter and an Arduino-based monitoring system further contributes to improving the overall charging process for electric vehicles.

III.BLOCK DIAGRAM OF SOLAR-BASED FAST TAG BATTERY CHARGER FOR ELECTRIC VEHICLE

Fig-1. Block Diagram of Solar-Based Fast Tag Charger for Electrical Vehicle

Ac Main Supply:

An alternating current of 230v,50Hz is taken from the utility.

Bridge Rectifier:

A bridge rectifier makes utilize of four diodes in a bridge course of action to accomplish full-wave amendment. This is a broadly utilized setup, both with person diodes wired as appeared up and with single component bridges where the diode bridge is wired insides.

Solar Panel

Fig-2: Solar panel

The solar cell harnesses sunlight to generate electricity and converts it from AC to DC current. The DC current is then directly linked to the battery. The solar cell employed has a power output of 12 watts. As we move toward developing our prototype into a marketable product, we plan to incorporate MPPT technology into our system to enhance efficiency and reliability in meeting the customer's energy demand.

Changeover Switch:

A changeover switch is an electrical switch that permits a stack to be changed from one electrical source to another and bad habit versa, either physically or naturally.

Charge Controller:

The charge controller functions as a crucial device that manages the flow of power from the charger to the battery, safeguarding the battery from potential harm caused by over-charging. Through the utilization of a microcontroller, the system can effectively monitor the battery levels and disconnect the charging source once the battery reaches full capacity, preventing overheating and damage. By integrating a microcontroller into the setup, various additional features and functionalities can be incorporated, such as real-time monitoring of battery status and ensuring adequate power supply for charging devices. This proactive approach not only enhances the overall efficiency of the system but also prevents potential issues by regulating the power flow effectively

Voltage/Current Sensor:

To degree voltage refinement over a circuit component, interface the sensor in parallel over the centers where voltage needs to be measured. This setup ensures that the voltage sensor has a through and through higher resistance compared to the interior resistance of the circuit. As a result, the voltage sensor draws as it were unessential current from the circuit, minimizing any unsettling impacts to the measured voltage.

Current sensors are associated in arrangement with the circuit, meaning the current streams through the ammeter itself. To dodge aggravating the measured current, ammeters are outlined with exceptionally moo resistance. Advanced ammeters utilize shunt resistors and inside circuitry to change over the current into a discernable esteem on its show.

Lithium – Ion Battery:

Fig-3: Lithium-Ion Battery

Lithium-Ion batteries are widely used in a majority of portable electronic devices like smartphones, laptops, and digital cameras because of their long-lasting power efficiency. They are the most popular type of rechargeable batteries known for their high energy density, minimal charge loss, and lack of memory effect. These batteries utilize Lithium ions to facilitate the flow of charge between the negative and positive electrodes during discharge and charging cycles. While recharging, an external current exceeding the battery's voltage is applied, causing the lithium ions to move back and forth between the electrodes, where they are absorbed into the porous electrode material through a process known as intercalation.

Arduino Uno:

The Arduino Uno is a development board that uses the ATmega328 microcontroller and is equipped with 14 digital input/output pins (6 of which can function as PWM outputs), 6 analog inputs, a 16 MHz ceramic resonator, a USB connection, a power jack, an ICSP header, and a reset button. It comes pre-installed with everything necessary to support the microcontroller, allowing users to easily connect it to a computer via USB or power it using an AC-to-DC adapter or battery to get started.

Fig-4:Arduino UNO

LCD Screen:

The LCD display has two rows, with each row capable of displaying up to 16 characters using a 5x7 dot matrix for each character. The display appearance depends on the control supply voltage and whether messages are shown in one or two lines, with a variable voltage of 0 to V_{dd} connected to V_{ee} for adjustment. A trimmer potentiometer is typically used for this purpose. Some versions of the display come with built-in backlighting using blue or green diodes, which require a current-limiting resistor when in operation, similar to LED diodes.

Fig-5: LCD Screen

Fire/Flame Sensor Module:

Fire sensors are highly responsive to standard light, making them ideal for fire detection purposes. They can detect fire or wavelengths in the range of 760 nm to 1100 nm of light. It is important to maintain a certain distance between the sensor and the fire to prevent damage from high temperatures. The sensor can be connected directly to a microcomputer's IO port via a small plate output interface and a single chip. It is recommended to test the sensor at a minimum distance of 80 cm, adjusting as needed if the fire is larger. With a detection angle of 60 degrees, the sensor is particularly sensitive to fires within its range.

Regulated Power Supply:

Control supplies are designed to convert high-voltage AC mains power into a suitable low-voltage supply for electronic circuits and devices. A regulated power supply (RPS) is a power supply that processes, filters, and regulates the AC mains to deliver a stable power supply for a microcontroller and other connected devices.

A control supply can be divided into a grid of sections, each with a designated function. When referring to a directed D.C control supply, it pertains to a direct current power source that maintains a constant output voltage regardless of fluctuations in the alternating current mains or load variations.

IV. DEVELOPMENT OF HARDWARE AND ITS WORKING

Fig-6: Development of hardware to solar-based fast tag battery charger for electric vehicle

We harness renewable solar energy to charge electric vehicles, utilizing solar cells to convert sunlight into DC electric current stored in a 12V battery. A solar charge controller regulates power supply from the solar panel, accounting for fluctuations due to factors like irradiance and temperature. By stabilizing the unregulated power input, the solar controller ensures consistent, reliable energy generation. The battery charger streamlines the charging process, reducing battery charging time compared to traditional methods. In summary, we leverage solar power through solar cells and a charge controller to efficiently charge electric vehicle batteries, optimizing the charging process for minimal environmental impact.

The Arduino serves as the central component of the system, providing an accessible and easily customizable platform for programming. It receives a dedicated 5V power supply to remain active for processing inputs and executing the operational program. Two distinct input methods are employed: RFID technology, including RFID Reader and RFID cards or tags, enables automatic detection and transmission of input data to the Arduino. Additionally, manual input is facilitated through the use of a keypad. The RFID tag, equipped with an integrated circuit and antenna, communicates with the RFID reader to provide input data. The keypad serves as an alternative method for users to input charging values for the EV

vehicle. These two input approaches collectively form the foundation of the system's input interface, enabling seamless interaction with the Arduino-based control unit for efficient EV charging management.

Encouraging information investigation and recording can be facilitated through the utilization of cloud computing, allowing for easy storage and analysis of data. Thing Talk enables the real-time transmission of information, which can then be stored for future analysis, facilitating the advancement of innovative product development. This progress is key in the establishment of an efficient framework for electric vehicle charging stations. When pursuing large-scale infrastructure development, important factors to consider include user utilization of charging stations and their willingness to pay a reasonable price for charging services. The integration of cloud computing and Thing Talk streamlines information handling, enhancing the efficiency of data processing for the improvement of electric vehicle infrastructure. Varied aspects such as user behavior at charging stations and their readiness to cover costs play crucial roles in the successful development of a robust charging network.

The diagram illustrates the arrangement of components in the prototype. The Arduino is responsible for processing input data and initiating the program. Initially, the voltage sensor interfaces with the battery to calculate and manage the essential voltage. Following this, the Arduino activates the relay to start a reverse countdown and close the circuit, enabling the current to flow from the circuit to the EV vehicle via the connected plug. A reverse timer displayed on the LCD informs the user about the necessary charging duration to achieve their desired charge level. Upon reaching the required charge level, the relay automatically opens the circuit, interrupting the current flow, allowing the user to disconnect the plug from the vehicle

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A customary family outlet (15A plug) can charge the existing EV by means of AC control. There is a greatest charging control of 2.3kW for AC charging. The charging time will be 8 to 9 hours utilizing AC control, But by utilizing a DC charger we can diminish the charging time of 1 to 2 hours for charging in the extend of 2 to 20kW control.

VI. CONCLUSION

By utilizing solar power, the charger reduces reliance on grid electricity, thus contributing to the integration of renewable energy sources into the power grid. Solar energy is clean and renewable, leading to a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions compared to conventional fossil fuel-based charging methods. This aligns with efforts to mitigate climate change and reduce air pollution. Solar energy can significantly reduce operational costs over time since sunlight is free. EV owners may benefit from lower charging costs compared to traditional grid-based charging. Solar-based chargers can operate independently of the grid, making them suitable for remote locations or areas with unreliable grid infrastructure. This can improve access to charging facilities in underserved areas. Incorporating fast charging technology ensures quick replenishment of EV batteries, enhancing convenience for users and promoting EV adoption by addressing range anxiety concerns. Solar-based fast chargers support the transition to sustainable transportation by encouraging the adoption of electric vehicles, thus reducing reliance on fossil fuels and promoting energy independence.

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